

**KNOWING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE-IMPROVING THE RATING OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN****Avliyakulova Fotima Nusratovna**

the master of master's degree, Navoi state pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10142874>

In ancient times, in order to obtain and improve knowledge, many of our compatriot scientists sought to obtain accurate, reliable information directly from the original source, manuscripts. Because violations were often allowed when transferring information from mouth to mouth or copying from the original manuscripts.

For example, our great scientists Imam Al-Bukhari (one of the great works is the collection of Hadith), Ibn Sino (one of the great works is the canon of medical medicine), Al-Beruni (mathematician, astronomer) have achieved world fame, whose works are still used by all mankind and the Muslim world due to the fact that for years they spent their lives in many countries outside their homeland, learning and collecting reliable information from the original source and the original manuscripts for their works.

Returning, at present we can say that there is a rapid development of information and communication technologies, which allows or gives an opportunity to qualitatively raise the level of knowledge of all civilized humanity on earth. With the help of the Internet, Telegram channels and social networks, any information from the original source in all directions has become available to humanity in international languages (English, Russian, Chinese, etc.).

Currently, people sitting at home at a computer, laptop or using a smartphone have the opportunity to look into any corner of the world, watch or read all the world news and achievements in all fields. However, all this information is sanctified in foreign languages. And when translating, distortions are often allowed, when an incorrect translation of one word can distort the meaning of the entire sentence, or even the entire text. Therefore, in order to be aware of all reliable world events and achievements, it is necessary to know foreign languages, as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan has repeatedly said in his speeches.

To achieve these goals, it is necessary to comprehensively make great efforts to study foreign languages, starting with preschool institutions, schools and universities.

It would not be bad to develop and implement for each stage (preschool institutions, schools, universities) its own unique methodology for learning each foreign language, otherwise we will not achieve great success quickly and efficiently. For example, if we take education in schools, there were times, and even now, when textbooks were changed several times without achieving the desired results.

It is necessary for every family to instill in their children a love for the book from childhood, as the head of our state often says in his speeches. Working with the book lays a solid foundation for the harmonious and comprehensive development of the child and the perception of the world. It is necessary to publish more books with color illustrations, informative and fascinating.

In recent years, some of the young people have experienced great relaxation in their attitudes towards the book. This is due to the fact that mostly young people got carried away and switched to the electronic version of obtaining information using the Internet and social networks. It's a disease. In medicine, there are such diseases that need to be treated from the inside with pills, and from the outside with ointment. They say that when the medicine from the inside and outside meet, the disease is cured.

Therefore, I think that in order to cure the disease, **it is necessary to develop and implement books with QR codes with voice voicing and explanation of the topic being studied for all stages of training**, which will allow the user to independently and quickly (in preschool institutions under adult supervision) fix the topic being studied. This method will allow you to simultaneously use the classic version of obtaining knowledge by reading books and modern achievements in the field of ICT. With the help of this technique, you can return to the times of pre-computer relations to the book.

I hope that all the youth of Uzbekistan will justify the trust of the President and the Government of Uzbekistan, will be more erudite, intelligent, knowing at least one foreign language and will make their worthy contribution to improve the rating and the entry of the Republic of Uzbekistan among the most advanced countries in the world.